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**Initial definition of the scientific challenges and
initial evaluation plan - Predicting near-Earth space
dynamics with Vlasiator**

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

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Executive Summary

This document outlines the scientific challenges for the Vlasiator plasma simulation code, as they are envisioned in the first year of the Plasma-PEPSC project. It gives an outline of the basic physical environment and state of the art of near-Earth plasma simulations that Vlasiator performs, and specifies a scientific target case which would be desirable to simulate within the timeframe of this EuroHPC project. Performance profiling of the current state of the Vlasiator system has been performed at various scales, and its results are being presented.

Based on the profiling data, performance extrapolation to the scientific target case shows that Vlasiator currently has a performance gap of a factor 52 compared to what would be required. We discuss further steps in the development of the simulation code to address this gap, and give an overview of the planned improvements to the code.

Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Definition of the Scientific Challenge	7
2.1	Relevance and Physical Background	7
2.2	Detailed Definition of the Simulation Setup	7
3	Gap analysis	8
3.1	Downscaling the Target Case	8
3.2	Initial Performance Analysis	8
3.3	Performance Projection to the Target Case for Exascale	10
4	Roadmap for Development	12
4.1	Identification of Bottlenecks in the Current Code	12
4.2	Next Steps Planned	12
5	Software Engineering Status and Plan	13
5.1	Copyright and license	13
5.2	Development process and coding standards	13
5.3	Bug tracking	14
5.4	Documentation and user support	14
5.5	Requirements handling	14
5.6	Continuous Integration and Testing	14
5.7	Release process	15
5.8	Deployment	15
5.9	Deprecation	15
6	Conclusion	15

1 Introduction

Figure 1: Example snapshot of the physical domain of a Vlasiator simulation of Earth's magnetosphere. Earth is located in the centre of the domain, and the solar wind arrives at supersonic speeds from the $+x$ direction. Interaction with Earth's dipole magnetic field forms a bow shock, magnetosheath, magnetotail as well as a multitude of kinetic plasma effects.

The solar wind, a continuous stream of plasma emanating from the Sun, interacts with the Earth's magnetosphere resulting in possibly adverse space weather. During geomagnetic storms, systems like power grids and satellite positioning systems are at risk due to enhanced particle radiation and disturbances of the geomagnetic field, potentially leading to large-scale blackouts and global disruption of communications. The strongest historical storms even resulted in aurorae visible in the Caribbean. The grand challenge in predicting space weather risks and modelling powerful geomagnetic storms is to encompass the whole of near-Earth space with an ion-kinetic description, while simulating the whole system for the duration of a typical geomagnetic storm, lasting from a few hours to several days, with up to extreme driving conditions (order-of-magnitude increases in solar wind speed, density, and magnetic field magnitude). To properly model the geomagnetic response, the ion-kinetic plasma model must be coupled to a model capable of describing ionospheric currents and feedback.

Vlasiator [1, 2] is the world’s first (and currently only) simulation code that is able to model Earth’s entire Magnetosphere (Figure 1) using a hybrid-Vlasov approach, in which the kinetics of ions are represented through their 6-dimensional phase space distribution function. This approach is numerically quite expensive, but allows kinetic phenomena to be resolved (unlike in magnetohydrodynamics or other fluid approaches), while not suffering from particle sampling noise that is inherent to Particle-in-Cell simulations. The Vlasiator research group’s publication history shows that hybrid-Vlasov simulations are nowadays a viable tool, and are able to resolve physical phenomena not accessible to other approaches.

2 Definition of the Scientific Challenge

Our goal is to run simulations of Earth’s magnetosphere at unprecedented fidelity, surpassing the state of the art in resolution for kinetic simulations. Further, we endeavour to move the simulations’ inner boundary further inwards, towards increasing magnetic field strengths, and thus more stringent constraints on simulation timesteps.

2.1 Relevance and Physical Background

Ion dynamics in near-Earth space have characteristic length scales defined by both the magnetic field strength B (which directly relates to the ion Larmor radius $r_L = \frac{m_i v_{\perp}}{q_i B}$ of ions with charge q_i and mass m_i) and the plasma density (which affects the ion inertial length $r_i = c/\omega_{pi}$). While simulations with coarser resolution length scales have merit (compare [3]), study of kinetic plasma effects at full fidelity would benefit from full resolution of both these length scales.

As the magnetic field strength B above Earth’s polar region rises steeply the closer one comes to the inner boundary, resolution constraints of a simulation become more and more stringent the further in its inner boundary condition is located. Alas, it is also exactly in the regions closest to Earth where a multitude of kinetic plasma physics regions of interest are located, such as the ring current, radiation belts, plasmasphere and exosphere.

Hence, in order to access these regions with Vlasiator’s kinetic simulation abilities, a development effort is underway to increase Vlasiator’s computational performance such that the inner boundary can be pushed inwards and the overall spatial resolution of global magnetospheric simulation runs can be increased.

2.2 Detailed Definition of the Simulation Setup

In the context of attaining our aforementioned scientific goals, we are aiming for simulating:

- A simulation of global coupling of Solar Wind↔Magnetosphere↔Ionosphere in a simulation box that contains part of the solar wind and extends to at least $-100 R_E$ in the tail. The overall physical size of the simulation box directly correlates with the computational intensity of a simulation.

- The inner simulation boundary should be located at $2.5 R_E$ (or further in). As the magnetic field strength of Earth’s dipole field rises sharply close to Earth ($B \sim r^{-3}$), this creates a numerical challenge: The plasma’s Larmor frequency $\Omega = \frac{q_i B}{m_i}$ needs to be resolved by the simulation timestep. Thus, this parameter affects computational scaling by a factor of $1/x^3$.
- Spatial resolution of the simulation mesh (at the highest refinement level) should be 500 km or finer. This means one additional refinement level compared to the current top-end Vlasiator simulations, and a factor of 8 more field solver cells.
- The run should continue for at least 2 simulated hours, about four times as long as the current record.
- As opposed to the current homogeneous solar wind inflow conditions, the inflowing solar wind conditions should be time-varying (representing realistic solar wind transient effects, like turbulent CME sheath regions or flux ropes).
- The outer size of the simulation domain should be chosen so that it includes Earth’s wave foreshock structure, with its spatially varying and complex structure of velocity distribution functions.
- We want to be able to automatically make decisions about dynamic mesh refinement and subgrid modelling at run-time, in order to track the physical phenomena of interest with maximum possible fidelity.

3 Gap analysis

3.1 Downscaling the Target Case

The physical setup for the target case, simulation of the entire magnetosphere of Earth, has been the research focus of the Vlasiator research group at the University of Helsinki for the last decade already. As such, simulations with lower resolution, dimensionality and physical fidelity have been performed, studied and published in the past [1].

Hence, magnetospheric simulation data from a recent large-scale Vlasiator computing campaign (Run on LUMI-C thanks to the EuroHPC JU computing grant “MICK”) can be immediately employed as a downscaled analogon of the target case. In addition, lower resolution runs of small magnetospheric setups have been run to provide scaling analysis to facilitate performance extrapolation towards the target case scales. Table 1 shows resolution and boundary parameters of the runs we chose for this performance extrapolation. Note that they do not formally follow weak-scaling or strong-scaling schemata, but represent typical scientific use cases of the Vlasiator code at the selected scale, such that extrapolation to the target case can also be treated as a realistic estimate.

3.2 Initial Performance Analysis

Vlasiator operates on a 6-dimensional, sparse, refined Eulerian mesh of phase space, updating each phase space cell at every simulation timestep. In addition, Vlasiator’s

Machine	Nodes	Δx (km)	r_i	Steps
LUMI-C	1	4000	$10.3 R_E$	190
LUMI-C	8	4000	$10.3 R_E$	40
Mahti	50	2000	$4.7 R_E$	84
LUMI-C	250	1000	$4.7 R_E$	71
Target		500	$2.5 R_E$	

Table 1: Parameters of the downscaled target cases compared to the scientific target case.

field solver solves Maxwell’s equations in three dimensions, using a uniformly discretized, cartesian mesh at higher temporal resolution (see [4] for details of these two meshes and their coupling).

The simulation’s main loop computing time contributions can thus be decomposed into three groups:

- *Vlasov solvers* proper. These are specifically the **Spatial-space** and **Velocity-space** solvers which comprise the solution of the Vlasov equation for ions. As they operate on the 6-dimensional phase space data structure holding the phase space density values, their computational effort is expected to scale proportional to the overall phase space cell count of the simulation.
- *Field solver*. The time group **Propagate-Fields** contains the solver to update electromagnetic field quantities on the fully refined 3-dimensional field solver grid. This solver’s numerical effort is independent of the phase space complexity, but instead scales with the number of field solver grid cells in the simulation, as well as simulation quantities such as magnetic field strength and plasma density.
- *Others*, including the steps **Ionosphere-solve**, **I/O**, **Balancing load** and **Compute timestep**. In the scope of the profile runs, these have had a negligible impact on total runtime and are not further considered in this document.

As the two primary solver groups scale very differently with respect to the target cases’ requirements, it makes sense to define two separate figures of merit to extrapolate overall simulation performance:

- FOM_V is the performance in 6D phase space cell updates per walltime second, quantifying the performance of the Vlasov equation solver and related communication and I/O overhead, per compute node. This figure of merit is measured in *phase space cell updates / compute nodes / s*.
- FOM_F counts the number of field solver cell updates per walltime second, thus being a direct measure of the field solver performance. This, too, is normalized to the compute node count, thus measured in *field solver cells / compute nodes / s*

This diversification of the FOM measure compared to the initial formulation in the project proposal text (where only a single, combined FOM for the whole simulation loop was proposed) is motivated by the observation of the solvers’ very different scaling behaviour, and highlights the need for a focussed effort on streamlining the combined performance optimization and load balancing properties of both solvers.

We employed the TAU performance measurement and analysis tools [5] to obtain Vlasiator profile and trace. During a three-day workshop hosted by CSC–IT Center

Name	Exclusive TIME	Inclusive TIME	Calls	Child Calls
.TAU application	0.001	1,844.43	1	1
taupreload_main	0.001	1,844.429	1	17
main	0.002	1,842.288	1	4
Simulation	0.007	1,662.342	1	296
Propagate	0.003	1,558.669	71	513
Propagate Fields	0.054	668.607	71	16,330
Spatial-space	0.001	626.189	71	71
Velocity-space	0.003	164.332	71	213
Update system boundaries (Vlasov post-acceleration)	0.096	52.675	71	15,700
Update system boundaries (Vlasov post-translation)	0.099	34.415	71	15,753
Ionosphere-solve	10.31	10.326	4	4
fieldtracing-ionosphere-fsgridCoupling	0.023	2.063	4	64
ionosphere-mapDownMagnetosphere	0.007	0.035	4	12
Compute interp moments	0.013	0.013	142	0
ionosphere-calculateConductivityTensor	0.011	0.011	4	0
IO	0.008	80.645	72	364
Balancing load	0.032	16.713	4	924
compute-timestep	3.071	5.146	70	70
ionosphere-updatelIonosphereCommunicator	0	1.162	4	20
Shrink_to_fit	0.001	0.001	4	0
Project_endTimeStep	0	0	71	0
Initialization	0.001	179.906	1	10
report-memory-consumption	0.023	0.038	1	14
Finalization	0	0	1	0
MPI_Init_thread()	2.112	2.112	1	1
MPI_Finalize()	0.028	0.028	1	0
MPI_Corrm_free()	0	0	13	0
MPI_Corrm_rank()	0	0	1	0

Figure 2: Screenshot of TAU’s paraprof visual profiler, showing the hierarchical profile statistics table for a Vlasiator simulation run on one node of LUMI-C.

for Science in Espoo, Finland, the Vlasiator and TAU (from the University of Oregon) teams worked together to obtain high-fidelity profile and trace data of Vlasiator runs on EuroHPC’s LUMI-C and CSC’s Mahti system at different scales (compare figure 2). Magnetospheric simulations were performed on 1, 8, 50 and 250 nodes, with correspondingly different physical system sizes. Table 1 shows the physical resolution of these runs. Table 2 presents their resulting phase space block and field solver cell counts, as well as the performance figures of merit obtained from the scaling data.

Nodes	Machine	Phase space cells	Field solver cells	FOM _V (cells/s/node)	FOM _F (cells/s/node)
1	LUMI-C	462690240	100672	1.10×10^9	3.53×10^6
8	LUMI-C	6265064768	41779200	2.04×10^9	2.02×10^6
50	Mahti	44944217984	49836032	8.03×10^8	1.01×10^6
250	LUMI-C	576607116352	554696704	6.29×10^8	2.36×10^5

Table 2: Simulation phase space / fieldsolver cell sizes and figures of merit for the down-scaled target cases of Vlasiator global magnetospheric runs.

3.3 Performance Projection to the Target Case for Exascale

Taking the phase space block counts and field solver cell numbers of our profiling test runs (Table 2), we can provide an educated guess what their scale numbers will be given the scientific target case outlined in Section 2:

Figure 3: Scaling behaviour and performance extrapolation of Vlasiator’s Vlasov (violet) and field solvers (green). Performance FOMs are plotted over their corresponding computational scale reference. Estimates for the scientific target case scales are given by the dashed vertical lines.

- Moving the inner simulation boundary from $4.7 R_E$ to $2.5 R_E$ causes the simulation timestep to be smaller by a factor 6.8, meaning a $6.8x$ increase in computational effort to simulate the same physical time.
- $2\times$ spatial resolution in three spatial dimensions means an $8\times$ increase in both phase space and field solver cells compared to the 250-node profiling run. This also leads to a $8\times$ smaller fieldsolver timestep, as it scales like $\Delta t_f \sim \Delta x^3$.
- Running the simulation twice as long comes with a directly proportional $2\times$ increase in computational effort
- The remaining aforementioned scientific requirements are not expected to have a direct correlation with overall computational effort.

In Figure 3, both phase space block counts and field solver cell counts were extrapolated by multiplying by a factor of 8 compared to the 250 node run (depicted as the dashed vertical bars in the figure). Both solver performance figures of merit were extrapolated to this scale by a simple power-law fit, yielding FOM values for the Vlasov solvers and field solver at the target scale:

- FOM_V (Vlasov solvers): 5.13×10^8 cells/s/node
- FOM_F (Field solver): 2.98×10^5 cells/s/node

If a simulation at this scale were to be run on 800 nodes of LUMI-C, the corresponding timestep walltime can be extrapolated to be $\Delta t_{\text{Vlasov}} \approx 11.25$ s for the Vlasov solvers and $\Delta t_{\text{Field}} \approx 74$ s for the field solver, yielding a total $\Delta t = \Delta t_{\text{Vlasov}} + \Delta t_{\text{Field}} = 85.25$ s for one simulation timestep.

Given the increase of required simulation timesteps by a factor of 32, we estimate a total amount of $n = 1.7 \times 10^6$ timesteps required for the scientific target case outlined in section 2. Overall simulation walltime would hence result to 4.12×10^9 core-hours of computation time 800 nodes of LUMI-C.

The typical practice of supercomputing centres is to give out allocations of computing time on the order of 80 Mio core hours to “Grand Challenge” runs. Hence, the performance gap that Vlasiator will have to close in order to realistically run the scientific target case on a supercomputer is $G = \frac{8.29 \times 10^9 \text{ core-hours}}{80 \times 10^6 \text{ core-hours}} \approx 51.53$.

4 Roadmap for Development

4.1 Identification of Bottlenecks in the Current Code

The finegrained profiling and performance analysis data obtained via the Tau profile showed a clear picture that Vlasiator’s main performance hindrance is synchronization of MPI communication, evidenced by the fact that 27% of the overall simulation runtime in the 250-node run was spent in the `MPI_Waitall()` function. Concretely, this is caused by load imbalance between different simulation regions and tasks and despite Vlasiator’s already extensive effort for dynamic load rebalancing at runtime. While this bottleneck had per se been already known before the start of the Plasma-PEPSC project (and it is the primary motivation for UoH’s task leadership in WP 3’s load balancing efforts), its quantification and comparison to the other computational hotspots of the code has now made its importance even clearer.

A second, more concerning scaling bottleneck in the code that has been identified as part of this profiling process is the behaviour of the field solver at scale. In production scale simulation runs throughout the last couple of years, the Vlasiator field solver accounted for only about 10% of the total simulation runtime, yet its total runtime percentage in the 250 node scaling run on LUMI-C amounts to a worrying 42%. It appears that the field solver in its current implementation has met its scaling limits and its communication structure needs to be reorganized. The scaling extrapolation analysis presented in Figure 3 implies that its runtime fraction would only get worse at larger scales.

4.2 Next Steps Planned

Exploration of new load balancing methods and improvement of Vlasiator’s overall MPI parallelism is the next step on the Vlasiator team’s roadmap (through its leadership of WP 3 and the load balancing Task 3.2 therein). Specifically, we are investigating alternative spatial decomposition algorithms already provided by the Zoltan library and comparing their relative benefits for scalability.

In collaboration with the CSC Centre for Scientific Computing, Espoo, Finland, a code overhaul and performance optimization project for the field solver has started. Its focus lies on vectorization of the field solver, to generically increase its performance both on

current CPU architectures as well as the future scalable vectorization architectures on the EuroHPC roadmap. Further, a GPU accelerator port of the field solver is in its planning stage. In addition to the raw performance optimization of this solver, an architectural change in its task decomposition will be investigated, in which the field solver might plausibly run on only a subset of the MPI node set in any given Vlasiator run. The lower effective node count should increase the efficiency of the MPI communicators used inside the solver’s ghost cell update functionality and thus be beneficial for overall simulation scalability.

Beyond the concrete code improvements that target the performance bottlenecks visible in the profiler, there are multiple parallel ongoing efforts in the Vlasiator team to enhance both the underlying physical model and its computational architecture for future performance gains.

As the simulations’ time resolution is strongly varying throughout the domain, a change of the overall solver schedule from a fixed, global timestep towards a classification of simulation cells into separate subcycling domains (which we refer to as “Time classes”) is in the works. This change, once fully implemented, will particularly alleviate the high cost incurred from moving the simulations’ inner boundary inwards, as the inner parts of the domain will only locally require higher-cadence timestepping.

GPU porting of the remaining solvers (Ionosphere, Vlasov acceleration and translation) are also in the works and are showing promising preliminary performance numbers. Once the entirety of Vlasiator’s main loop has GPU implementations available, data locality can be shifted entirely from the CPU side into GPU memory, thus avoiding costly back-and-forth transfers of simulation data between CPU and GPU.

5 Software Engineering Status and Plan

Compared to the other codes represented in the Plasma-PEPSC project, Vlasiator was somewhat behind in its implementation of good software engineering practices.

5.1 Copyright and license

Vlasiator uses the GPLv2 license. Copyright currently lies entirely with the University of Helsinki and the Finnish Meteorological Institute (as these two institutions have provided all code contributions to date), but we are openly accepting contributions from external collaborators as well, which will lead to to fragmented copyright spread over all contributors.

5.2 Development process and coding standards

Vlasiator is hosted publicly on github (<https://github.com/fmihpc/vlasiator>). Only the core development team has push rights to the repository. The branch structure is a stable “master” branch and a “dev” branch in which individual feature branches are accumulated via pull requests. All PRs are reviewed by typically two members of the core team before they are merged.

There is a style guide (<https://github.com/fmihpc/vlasiator/wiki/Coding-Style>). Compliance with the style guide is loosely enforced during code reviews of the core team.

5.3 Bug tracking

The github issue tracker is used exclusively for issue tracking. The core development team manages it.

5.4 Documentation and user support

On a high, conceptual level, the code's function is documented in a sporadically-updated living reviews article [1]. This serves mostly as the citeable scientific reference for the code's function. User documentation is provided in the github wiki pages (<https://github.com/fmihpc/vlasiator/wiki>). These are not systematically kept up-to-date and are thus rather incomplete. Autogenerated doxygen documentation exists for maybe 50%. We strive to improve and expand the documentation throughout the scope of the Plasma-PEPSC project.

5.5 Requirements handling

Hardware requirements for main production simulation runs are primarily determined by the availability and architecture of supercomputing environments that we get access to. In order to maintain maximum flexibility and portability, the code is locally run and maintained on a variety of different-sized platforms.

The Vlasiator science team at the University of Helsinki determines the requirements (both in terms of hardware support and features) based on its own scientific goals. External contributors are themselves responsible for adding features that they require, and the core development team supports them in integrating them into the trunk codebase.

5.6 Continuous Integration and Testing

An integration test package exists as part of the source tree. It contains test setups for all major solver components, but a coverage amount is hard to quantify. Tests are compared to previous, known-good simulation outputs in both produced outputs and runtime performance. The test package is not integrated into any automatic testing framework, it needs to be invoked manually and results need to be evaluated by eye. Unit tests currently exist only for small parts of the code, more comprehensive introduction of tests is on our roadmap for the second year of Plasma-PEPSC.

When access to a new HPC system is obtained (or after significant system upgrades), testpackage runs are typically performed with all available compilers on the system to find best performance. Further, the whole test package is typically run by the core team before any nontrivial pull request is merged into the dev branch. Usual testing is performed at the University of Helsinki's "Carrington" cluster, provided by the Finnish Grid and Cloud Initiative (FGCI).

A continuous integration process has recently been set up on the basis of GitHub actions at the start of the Plasma-PEPSC project and is slowly being integrated into the day-to-day development activities.

5.7 Release process

Releases are made by common agreement of the core development team. Typically, they coincide with publication of major breakthrough papers or reporting requirements for funding grants of the code. Version numbers are in Major.Minor form, with major releases coinciding with significant changes or enhancement of the physical model or simulation grids and minor version numbers signifying performance and/or stability improvements.

5.8 Deployment

Vlasiator (and its library dependencies) need to be manually downloaded and compiled following the installation instructions (<https://github.com/fmihpc/vlasiator/wiki/Installing-Vlasiator>). Manual tuning and adaptation of optimization flags and scheduler environment is required for every HPC platform. No automatic mechanism exists.

A complete list of software dependencies is maintained in the wiki of the main code repository. They are typically updated only when compiler or platform incompatibilities require an update.

5.9 Deprecation

There is currently no structured process for removal of old features. At irregular intervals, decisions about removal of features is made when they become a burden, but usually they are retained if they are not in the way.

6 Conclusion

The Vlasiator plasma simulation code tackles a challenging and state-of the art problem, namely kinetic simulations of near-Earth space in 6 dimensions. The scientific goals and numerical scaling for the coming years both provide a steep bar to scale.

Through profiling of supercomputer simulation runs on multiple scales, and subsequent performance extrapolation of the simulation solvers, we have determined that the Vlasiator code currently has a factor 52 performance gap compared to what it would require in order to run our envisioned scientific target case on a realistic scale at the end of the Plasma-PEPSC project period.

We have outlined our further development road map and plans to enhance our efficiency, in order to tackle this performance gap on EuroHPC machines.

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